
CHANGING ROLE OF COLLEGE LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS IN DISSEMINATING INFORMATION OF USER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on changing role of Library professional in Disseminating Information of user education. Library is integral part of academic library. It is power house it is a substation wherever information is collected, created, and assigned to satisfy the user's requirements. Traditionally libraries estimated themselves into words about their area, transaction, circulation but change though those steps do not include nature of service. The patrons are not always friendly among the information sources. So the important task of the college is to make sure that the library is used in the most profitable manner in this scenario user education play vital role in providing information sources according information needs. Advancements into the educational schemes become produced regarding variations toward the pedagogy systems which influence students Information seeking behavior. User study programs must be seated near the place meanwhile some educational libraries to support users obtain active usage of libraries.

Key words: *User Education, Information Resources and Service, ICT*

Introduction:

Change is always permanent and also nature of the law. So the library is not exceptions to this. Library is a big asset of any college. It has to grow not only in term of collection but also there is need to bring the versatile collection in the eyes of patrons of colleges. It is the responsibility of library professionals to bring into notice of teachers and students, how to make the use of it, various types of services offered. ICT play vital role in providing new skills for seeking information, retrieving, managing and processing for the patrons. Modernization and improvement of information and communication techniques and application has brought drastic change in the entire library management system, because of it

the onus has shifted from traditional model to 2.0 models. With the help of this users are getting information in stipulated time. The demand and expectation of library patrons is also changed thus modifying and simplifying the work nature of Librarian professional. The thought of a traditional library is developing into words of the kinds of records, assistance, collection of sources, techniques of information retrieval of accessible resources. The global changes have great impact as functioning of libraries; because of it user's expectation from libraries has increased.

Definition:

Conference was organized by American Library Association on use of

Education in 1876 in this conference the term User Education was first coined by S.S.Green. In which the meaning and importance of users education was discussed and concluded to have proper plan programme for it.

The term such as Library Orientation, Library Instruction and Bibliographic instruction are being used by the professionals for user education. There are many definitions available in the literature on USER EDUCATION. Which as follows.

Nancy Fjalbrant and Ian Malley said that user education is “concerned with the whole information and communication process and one part of this involved the total Interaction of user with the library.

User education is also instruction which covers library patrons with skills to enable them to be independent and sophisticated users of libraries and their resources.

Aim of User Education:

The aim of User education is to create awareness of the existing sources of information and to make them capable in locating, retrieving and use of information.

- To enhance the ability of students to think logically and do the things creatively.
- To make them aware in finding particular items with the help of catalogues, opac indexes, abstracts bibliographic etc.
- To make them aware about the tools and techniques of information technology to be used for information search.
- To provide users with the basic skills of literature searching.

Need of User Education:

- Some of the factors which necessitate the introduction of user education programs are as follows.
- Due to information explosion large amount of publication in variety of forms is generated with widely scattered manner.
- Change in the examination pattern, stressing on assignments, self study.
- Changes in teaching and learning method.
- Application of ICT tools in library for information storage, retrieval and dissemination.
- Increase in awareness about students requirements.
- Contribution of Internet in enhancing the search effectively
- The growth of information and students increasing information needs are of variety and diversity of level, frequency, volume and use.

Planning and Implementation:

Programme and Planning of user education programme is very important, particularly in academic college libraries. It requires proper planning and implementation of it. It includes;

- Orientation
- Bibliographic Instruction,
- Designing of right evaluation methods.
- Preparation of instructional materials.
- Testing Programme on small portion of user’s population.
- To generate sample of syllabus which includes information about Library Documents, Information Technology in Library,

Classification, and Reference Sources etc.

Levels of User Education:

Rathore (1992) summarized the different levels of user Education as follows,

1. At the beginning of every academic Year or every semester. It includes those students who have taken admission for the first time in college for various courses like B.A/B.Com/B.Sc...etc. They should be given basic introduction about the college library as well as information about various tools available in library like Library catalogue (OPAC), various reference sources, Periodicals available in the library, about collection of library etc.
2. Subject Oriented information when users are admitted to special branch or subject of their choice. This includes students enrolled at post-graduate level viz M.A, MCom, MSc, M.B.A etc. In addition with general information about library they should be informed about classification scheme , various types of services, literature search, compilation of bibliographies for their projects, technical writing etc.
3. Literature searching training to be given at initial stage of research work. It includes information about technical writing, giving footnotes etc.

Therefore depending upon the level of User education Library Professionals should set their Aims and Objectives of disseminating information of user education.

Challenges:

Main challenge is to shift the onus from traditional users into ICT based user.

- Sometimes complexity in electronic resources discourages he

students in using Information resources.

- Effective and Efficient way of services from library professionals
- To recognize the exact need and satisfy Information needs of the users.
- Research on complex and interdisciplinary topics.
- To identify and develop correct search strategy
- To cope up with advance information and disseminate in proper manner
- To develop library activities based on string services so as to satisfy their needs Information services should be developed keeping in mind the Users need in future.

Library Activities towards User Education:

Development in the Educational System has brought about changes in the teaching and learning methods which impact on students Information Seeking Behavior. Thus User Education Programmes and Various types of Library Activities have been put in place in college libraries to assist users for making effective use of libraries.

According to Fleming (1990) User education includes various programmes of instruction, educational and exploration provided by the libraries for users to enable them to make more effective and efficient and independent use of information sources and services to which these libraries provide access”.

Accordingly Libraries should arrange users education activities like Visit to Library, Book Talk, Book Exhibitions, Orientation Programme, Showing educational related film/Movies/organizing Quiz/Debates etc.

Role of Library Professionals in User Education:

Today's library is also described as Substation wherever information is collected, invented, and assigned to satisfy the user's wants. Library experts need to have an accurate understanding of the user's requirements. Externally understanding the information needs about its users that remain trying to implement useful assistance to them Traditionally Information sources are accessible into various ways viz, journals, research paper, book, etc. But in today's Information Technology era maximum students try to find information through internet .So it is responsibility of Library professionals to make the user aware about E-Journals and E-Books .online catalogs and their search procedures...etc Web based Education not only provides platform of interaction but also gives more Information technology Flexibility to the users The new social media like Blogs, twitters, face books , library websites play vital role in disseminating web based user education . Library professionals should provide such Internet based education that helps the students in giving knowledge of how to use Library OPAC, How to find out books, Magazines, Biographical data and related documents, method of selecting relevant database and other electronic resources. Library professionals are responding to the challenges of new technologies by taking the opportunity to their traditional role to Information base role.

With the help of mobile phones, tablets, and other related medium convert extra common and affordable, wireless technology can dramatically enhance learning and bring digital content to learners.

SMS-based Reference/Text Services can be offered to the students for

simple questions such as dictionary definitions, facts or services information from the library that can be answered with a brief response. Therefore a proper form including effective evaluation requires looking while pioneering social networks in the library. Users needed to conscious and adequate preparation should survive given to staff to accomplish the task of organizing social software in the library.

Benefits of User Education:

1. User education helps students in identify information needs; evaluate information in educational environment today.
2. Motivates Self-directed learning.
3. Appreciation for life –long learning
4. Multimedia content transfer and invention rights.
5. Constant and established getting help.

Conclusion:

Today's era of Information and technology has made users easy for direct access of Information, but at the same time there is need of information skill to collect and present that information. Thus making the job of Library professional more challenging. A quick change from traditional services to Information technology base service has made college libraries to show academic performance. Finally User education programmes should be made compulsory and it should be taken at the commencement of each semester. Class rooms of the college can be used for conducting lectures, but practical should be given in the library itself. This will not only increase the level of library bur it will also enhance the reputation of college and in turn promotes the use of library materials.

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